

Hydrogen Production from Biomass: Several Routes and Current Advancements

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Abstract:

The management of waste biomass is a significant challenge the human race is facing currently. General method of such waste management is either burning, or land filling. Other non-conventional methods applied are the anaerobic digestion (AD) of the waste and production of a combination of methane (CH₄) and other gases, generally known as "Biogas". But CH₄ is a green-house gas and the process has its own disadvantages. This article sheds light on production of hydrogen (H₂) from biomass in various pathways viz. Thermo-chemical conversion, microbial conversion etc. Various microbial pathways are discussed. Also, the potential market of this clean and green energy, and governmental policies are described.

Keywords: Hydrogen, Thermo-chemical, Microbe, Methane, Anaerobic Digestion

1. Introduction

Management of waste has been a topic of discussion for a long time now. As the concept of sustainable development is gaining attention from various fields, alternative usage of wastes has found their way. Generally, the wastes which are used for alternative usage are biodegradable like agri-residue, municipal solid waste (MSW) etc. Population of India is huge and as a consequence, India produces a lot of agricultural waste. Approximately 500 million tons of agricultural waste is generated in India per year. Lion share of this waste is used as fuel, food for domestic animals, and other domestic usage. Still around 92 million tons of waste is being burned [1]. The consequence of this burning is evident in the air quality index of Delhi, Haryana etc. during the later part of the year. Domestic management of these wastes generally means production of biogas, which contains 50% CH₄ approx, and final solid residues which can be used as fertiliser.

2. Traditional Management

Traditional management of biomass is processing it by AD. The agri-residues contain grass etc enriched in cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin etc. MSW contains paper, cardboard, brunch, rags etc. Generally these are enriched in carbohydrates, fats, proteins etc and are called complex organic compounds and also are subjected to AD. The process of AD is discussed below.

First step of AD is hydrolysis of complex organic compounds. This is achieved by hydrolytic

bacterias or synthetic enzymes. The result is simple organic compounds such as sugar, peptides etc. These are then subjected to acidogenesis by fermentative bacterias. The product produced is short chain fatty acid. This is then processed by acetogenesis by H₂ producing bacteria. The result of this acetogenesis is various acetic acids, H₂ and CO₂. In the last step, these are used as the raw material for methane production by methanogenesis. A short visual summary is given below (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The Process of AD

3. Benefits of Hydrogen

Over many years, the driving force for development of novel energy sources are many fold, ranging from availability to end-user demand. Increased pollution, cost-effectiveness, sustainable development, global warming etc. are the driving force in this period. Also, high consumption, limited source, and pollution caused by fossil fuels plays a significant role in new energy source development. In the context of waste management, CH₄ production is the most popular way. But as stated earlier, it is a greenhouse gas, and pollutes when used. All conventional methods for production of CH₄ leaves a carbon footprint. In contrast, H₂ has several advantages. The production methods of H₂ emit less or no greenhouse gas. If produced from biomass, it offers a -ve CO₂/H₂ ratio, meaning CO₂ is being captured in the process of production. Also, India has focused on H₂ production from an early stage. Various policies and roadmaps are being designed, implemented and deployed in various sectors for successful transition to H₂ based energy distribution and later dominate the H₂ based energy market internationally [2].

4. Hydrogen Production

Hydrogen production can be done in various ways from biomass. Mainly it can be categorised in three ways. The first and most popular way is Thermo-Chemical conversion. Next method is electrolysis conversion. And the last is to follow the microbial conversion. These conversion methods can be categorised further. Thermo-Chemical and microbial conversion methods are described below with a focus on recent progresses.

4.1. Thermo-Chemical Conversion

4.1.1 Introduction

As the name suggests, biomass is treated by chemicals and then is subjected to heat in this process. The biomass generally used in this process, called lignocellulosic biomass, is enriched in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Also some proteins and inorganic components such as N, S, Cl etc. are found in small quantities [3]. Tree branches, wood chips, agri-residues etc are suitable for being processed in this way. The biomass is subjected to pretreatment before being processed further. The pretreatment can be of three kinds. They are Physical Pretreatment, Chemical and Physicochemical Pretreatment, and Biological Pretreatment. The physical methods consist of milling, irradiation etc. The chemical methods consist of explosion, alkaline treatment etc. And biological methods consist of treatment by living organisms such as fungi etc [3].

4.1.2 Classification

The thermo-chemical conversion can again be classified into roughly seven types. The first being *Combustion*. In this case, the biomass is used as a reactant in the exothermic reaction. The heat is generated as the result of the reaction between O_2 in air and carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, sulphur etc in the biomass. Various types of combustion techniques are used; fixed-bed combustion, fluidized-bed combustion are some to name. This method is the most popular method for thermo-chemical conversion, and accounts for 90% of energy recovered from biomass currently [3]. The second method is *Carbonization*. The main feature of this method is carbonization of organic residues by pyrolysis. This can again be categorized in Hydrothermal Carbonization and Microwave-Assisted Hydrothermal Carbonization. Wood chips, food waste etc. are optimal for this kind of conversion. The third method is *Gasification*. It is the conversion of solid raw biomass to useful gaseous or liquid fuel. The gaseous fuel is generally known as "Syngas". Often compared to combustion and pyrolysis, this method is unique in its own way. The main goal of combustion is to produce heat energy whereas for gasification, the main goal is to produce fuel. Although it can be seen as a form of pyrolysis, where the temperature is high. Several catalytic agents are also used to decrease the working temperature. The method can be further classified as fixed-bed gasifier, fluidized-bed gasifier, entrained flow gasifiers etc. The fourth method is *Pyrolysis*. This is defined as providing heat energy to a substance in absence of oxygen. The products of pyrolysis may vary depending on the material being pyrolyzed, heating rate, initial temperature etc. Generally the products are water, charcoal or char, pyrolysis oils or tars and gases like CH_4 , H_2 etc. This method can again be classified into various categories viz. slow pyrolysis, fast pyrolysis, hydrolysis. The fifth method is known as *Liquefaction*. Liquefaction is the process of producing liquid or gaseous products from biomass in presence of water. Often, for this reason, it is termed as Hydrothermal Liquefaction. The working temperature of this method is less than that of pyrolysis, but the pressure and residence time is more. In this case, the large molecules break into relatively small and unstable molecules, and then fuse back to create polymers and finally bio-fuels. The sixth method is *Co-Processing*. This method is the application of co-gasification and co-pyrolysis. It helps in reduction of CO_2 emission, S ash etc. The last method is *Hydrolysis*. Hydrolysis is said to be the most appropriate pathway for lignocellulosic biomass [3]. Targeted hydrocarbons are easier to produce in this way.

4.1.1. Reactors

There are various reactors available for thermo-chemical conversion. However they can be broadly classified into two categories. These are *Updraft* or *Counter-Current* and *Downdraft*

Figure 2: (a) Downdraft Reactor, (b) Updraft Reactor

or *Co-Current* reactors. The former is older. In this case the air needed is drawn from below and the current goes upwards, hence the name. The processing is done in the reactor and the product gas is collected from the upper chamber of the reactor. The advantages of this kind of reactor are relatively simple design, simple feed stock etc. The disadvantage is the channeling rate of O_2 . Any sudden fluctuation may cause an explosion. Also, the production and presence of tar in the final product is a topic of concern. The latter types of reactors are relatively new. The design is somewhat complex compared to the former. The air needed is often supplied above or at the zone of high temperature. As a result the tar produced is degraded by high temperature. The product is collected from below. The major disadvantage of this type of reactor is rigidity concerning the feedstock. Also the sheer pressure drop during the process creates additional hindrance [4]. The schematic designs of both reactors are shown in Fig. 2.

4.1.2. Advancements In Current Technologies

Various studies have been going on for betterment of the reactor design. One of the most prominent works is from Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore (IISc), under the supervision of Dr. Dasappa. His team and he had been working on downdraft reactors and have attained one possible solution. The main problem of degradation of tar is answered in this design. The relative high time of residence and temperature causes the breakdown of tar. And they have designed it in such a way that the process remains isothermal. The product gases are enriched in hydrogen. The performance curve (Fig. 3) is shown below [4].

Figure 3: Performance curve of novel reactors

4.2. Microbial Conversion

Microbial conversion of biomass to hydrogen can be done in various ways. The basic methodology is to make culture feed from the feedstock of biomass. Later this is consumed by microbes and in the process, H₂ is produced. This H₂ is then collected and used. Below, some of the methods are described.

4.2.1 Production Through Cyanobactors

Cyanobactors are also blue-green algae. They are found in both freshwater and ocean. They have been a topic of interest since the late 1950s. Currently, they are being used in producing

the same species or in retrieving some biologically active components. Though their H₂ producing capabilities were discovered relatively recently. Three main enzymes are considered responsible for this. These are Nitrogenase or N₂ase, Reversible Hydrogenase or Hox, and Uptake Hydrogenase or Hup [5]. N₂ase can produce H₂ in two ways. One is while fixing N₂ directly. The reaction is shown below (Eq. 1).

It also is the case for Mo-Fe hydrogenase. Slight changes in the active site are observed in various other nitrogenases. The NH₃ produced can also contribute to other markets given its activity as fertiliser. If N₂ is not present, total electron flux is dedicated to the reduction of protons, thus producing H₂. Hence absence of N₂ is more preferred in production of H₂. Also, it is observed, the production rate shows an increment. It is because of active photosynthesis during day time and N₂ase is O₂ sensitive. Hox is also often called bidirectional hydrogenase. The presence of this enzyme was detected back in the 1970s [5]. Hox can produce H₂ in the dark, thus can be used alongside N₂ase for industrial usage. Hup acts in oxidation of H₂. These can be used for H₂ production from heterocystous and non-heterocystous cyanobactors.

4.2.1. Production Through Green Algae

Hydrogen production from green algae was first observed a long time ago [6]. The reason was unclear at that time. Through the advancements in current time, it is found that the H₂ is produced in a light-dependent way where water is broken down. The reaction is shown below (Eq. 2).

This is known as photoproduction of H₂. If applied industrially, it will be beneficial as the demand of the process is very less. If seen from the context of photosynthesis, production of H₂ is unfavourable and a waste material. Reduction of NADP⁺ is more favourable than of H⁺. Hence H₂ production was first observed in dark anaerobic conditions. Soon it was also observed that H₂ can be produced in light conditions. The hydrogenase, responsible for the enzymatic breakdown, is very sensitive to the presence of O₂. However, for industrial production of H₂, two major points are still needed to address. The first is the management of DCMU. DCMU is an inhibitor of electron transport. Hence it inhibits the production of H₂. The second is controlling the levels of O₂ during the process. This can be achieved by binding with other chemical groups.

4.2.2 Production Through Photofermentation

The process of photofermentation is observed in purple nonsulfur (PNS) bacteria. PNS bacteria can produce H_2 in anoxic conditions [7]. The enzyme responsible for this production is hydrogenase and N_2 ase. Now that it is evident, H_2 is also produced during N_2 fixation, the reaction in the case of PNS is shown below (Eq. 3).

It is quite similar to that of Eq. 1, but it differs stoichiometrically. However, production through N_2 ase is not the only thing. They have the ability to produce H_2 also through the activity of hydrogenase in sunlight. And, it is also a bidirectional one. The scheme is shown below (Eq. 4).

There is also slight variation in the stoichiometry depending on the variation of hydrogenase used during the process. The reaction, in terms of energy, is valuable. The main feature of PNS is the flexibility of the feedstock. Preferred substrate for this is low-molecular weight simple organic compounds, which can easily take part in the TCA cycle. The process can be applied to the waste water generated in several industries. Also the leftover final residue (if any), by the virtue of being biologically enriched, can be used as fertilizer. Some scientists have also tried to integrate this with the dark reaction for the production of H_2 simultaneously, as shown below (Eq. 5, 6).

4.2.3 Fermentative Hydrogen Production

Many types of production being discussed, it is worth noting that the fermentative route is preferred due to its supposed economical feasibility [8]. Fermentative hydrogen production follows the fermentative route. During fermentation, a low amount of H_2 is produced, the main product remains volatile fatty acids (VFA). Though, the exact product depends on various parameters like inoculum, feedstock, nutrients supplied, temperature, pH etc., but H_2 is produced in every case. Two cases are shown below (Eq. 7, 8) where H_2 is being produced from $C_6H_{12}O_6$, but the products and amounts are different.

4.2.4 Production Through Microbial Electrolysis

Production of H_2 with the help of microbial electrolysis is a relatively new concept. In this case, as the name suggests, electrolysis is done, but in the presence of some microbes. A new kind of cell is designed for this purpose and is termed as Microbial Electrolysis Cell (MEC) [9]. The process is somewhat similar to general electrolysis. There is a cathode, an anode, and a power supply. The novelty is that the cathode side and anode side are separated through a membrane and in the anode chamber some electrochemically active microbes are placed. In the anode chamber, biological residues will be broken down by the microbes and electrons and protons will be released in the process. As there is a potential gradient, generated by the power supply, released electrons and protons will follow their respective path to respective electrodes. This process is referred to as Bio-Electrochemically Assisted Microbial Reactor or BEAMR. The anode and cathode reactions are shown below respectively (Eq. 9, 10)

5. Potential Market

In India, most of H_2 is used for four purposes, viz. fertilizer, refineries, petrochemicals, and methanol. Though the industrial consumption of H_2 is likely to rise by 2050 by several fold [2]. Many other industries may use H_2 as their main power supply. The most prominent of them is iron and steel manufacturing. H_2 will be used as an alternative for their coal and natural gas based power supply. And gradually, H_2 will become the energy source. The main feature of H_2 based power supply is the green nature of it. Also it will actively reduce the carbon footprint. Various other industries have started to use H_2 for sustainable development. Various pilot projects have already been launched both internationally and nationally [2]. Some of them are production of caustic soda, automobile industry, transport sector etc. Also H_2 is likely to be utilised by electric power generation. Already, worldwide hype for electricity from non conventional sources is visible. Harnessing the power of H_2 will also ensure green production. Also local grid based energy generation and management can be done with H_2 , thus broadening its spectrum of application in both rural and urban areas as well as local and global use. Also industrial clusters may find it easy to manage the relation of surrounding areas if powered by hydrogen. Though it is worth noting that deployment of H_2 in various industries will be happening in different time frames and scales. And the main problem with usage of H_2 as of now is the transportation of it.

6. Governmental Policies

India has, from the beginning, set her eyes on commercial production, usage and spreading awareness for H_2 . Several steps are being taken by the Govt. of India for this eco-friendly energy source, preaching the global propaganda of “vasudhaiva kutumbakam” meaning “All is but family”. India also has considered the philosophy of “Local use, Global effect”. PM Modi had declared during the independence day celebration of 2021 that within 2047 India will be a hub for production of green hydrogen and will also export it [10]. As a direct effect, the Ministry of Power has issued a circular concerning future plans in february 2022 [11].

Certain considerations are kept in concern and may be deployed sooner or later. Various recommendations are also given to the govt. Some of them are discussed here. The first is cross-sectional coordination. As pointed out by TERI [2], H_2 will have a multitude of applications in various sectors, simultaneously. Hence without proper coordination in each level, the mammoth step will end up in veins. The second is shifting the perspective of researchers from R&D to commercialization. Various projects were sanctioned earlier for production of H_2 , but only from an R&D perspective. Now the government is likely to help institutions financially if they focus on commercial production of H_2 . The third is the introduction of emissions penalty. This will discourage existing industries to use traditional energy sources as there is high emission in those. Also it will be beneficial for the hydrogen project in its early stage. The fourth is creating the market through mandates and standards. Alongside penalizing emission and products created from them, the govt is looking forward to market and raising concerns about products produced in an eco friendly manner. This will ultimately help the end user to differentiate and acknowledge the green products. Also green products will be saved from the market competition with their rivals dominating the markets now. And lastly, it is advised to target the industries in the beginning phase, as alongside several institutions already focusing on hydrogen production, the R&D sectors of several industries may contribute heavily. Also transition to a new energy source is a huge step and will require help from the industries.

7. Conclusion

As pointed out in the article, H₂ has the potential to be the main energy source in a world where fossil fuels are finished. Production of H₂ as its own advantage from reducing global temperature to carbon capturing. Various pathways are there for the production but the most commercially successful one is the thermo-chemical route. Research works are going on to follow the biological route and are making certain progress. Several industries, now operating on fossil fuels, will have a lower emission rate and carbon footprint if switched to H₂ based power. The Government of India is focusing on hydrogen production more than ever. So this is high time for commercial production and use of hydrogen.

8. Acknowledgement

We would like to express our gratitude to the department of Biotechnology, Haldia Institute of Technology. Also we would like to thank our families and friends for their immense support during the work. Without their support, this work would have been dissolved.

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Souradipto Choudhuri

Souradipto Choudhuri is a final year student of Haldia Institute of Technology. He has been offered the role of Associate Analyst by Zifo R&D, a multinational company in the field of bioinformatics, in 2022. He has taken part in several national and international seminars. Also, he secured top 2% rank in an NPTEL exam. Mr. Choudhuri is a proficient python coder. He has worked with Boltzmann Labs and Rawal Genomics Labs. So far, he has published many articles in nationally acclaimed journals. Mr. Choudhuri also focuses on interdisciplinary projects. Currently he is associated with a project granted by MSME, a prototype

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Keya Sau

Dr. Keya Sau is currently working as an associate professor in Department of Biotechnology, Haldia Institute of Technology. Her research interest includes Computational analysis of genomes, proteomes and proteins and also structure, function, and stability of proteins of biotechnological importance etc. Dr. Sau has published twenty four research articles in the internationally reputed journals and many paper in national conferences. She acted as an invited speaker in the national and international seminars. She had received Scholarship from Govt. of West Bengal for extraordinary performances in both Secondary & Higher Secondary examination; Biotechnology Overseas Associateship Award from the Department of Biotechnology (DBT), Govt. of India; NIH Postdoctoral Fellowship from the United States of America for working under Prof. Chia Lee at the Department of Microbiology, UAMS, Little Rock, USA. Also she has received research grants on the project entitled “Structural investigation of the global virulence regulator SarA from *Staphylococcus aureus*” from the CSIR, Govt. of India.

**Education in Chemical Science and Technology,
Vol.- 12, February, 2023. ISBN: 978-81-958341-2-9**